

Synthesis, characterisation and antimicrobial studies of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of furan- and thiophene-2-aldoximes

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Abstract : Complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with furan- and thiophene-2-aldoximes have been synthesized. The structures of the synthesised compounds have been established by spectral and magnetic studies. All the synthesised complexes have been screened for their antimicrobial activities.

Keywords : Copper(II) complexes, nickel(II) complexes, cobalt(II) complexes.

The chemistry of coordination compounds with heterocyclic compounds containing oxygen and nitrogen as ligands has attracted increasing attention in recent years. It is well known that such ligands coordinate to a metal atom in different ways in different media. The oxime acts as an excellent ligand with nitrogen or oxygen as donor atoms. A number of complexes of oximes with transition metals are known. Studies of new types of chemotherapeutically important metal coordinated drugs are now attracting much attention¹. The aim of this study is to observe the impact of chelation on the therapeutic value of the organic compounds. Some Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of furan- and thiophene-2-aldoximes have been synthesised and characterised.

Furan-2-aldoxime (FO)

Thiophene-2-aldoxime (TO)

Results and discussion

Complexes Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with FO :

The analytical data reflect the metal to ligand stoichiometry to be 1 : 2 for Co^{II} and 1 : 1 for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}

complexes. The molar conductance value in methanol (10⁻³ M) suggests that the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes are non-electrolytic in nature (Table 1). All the complexes did not react with AgNO₃ solution indicating the non availability ionisable chloride ions and this confirms the chloride ion coordination in the complex.

In the IR spectrum of oxime, the band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ is observed at 1645 cm⁻¹. The shift to lower frequency (1625 cm⁻¹) in the metal complexes is due to coordination through oximino nitrogen² (Table 2). The band at 2920 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the ligand and that of the complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} can be assigned to ν_{OH} , indicating the non-involvement of oxygen atom of OH group in coordination. The N-O stretching frequency of the ligand at 1100 cm⁻¹ has shifted to 1080 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes corroborating coordination through oximino nitrogen. A band due to C-O-C (1131 cm⁻¹) of the ligand is shifted to lower frequency (1121 cm⁻¹) in complexes showing the involvement of ring oxygen in coordination³.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex shows two bands at 15340 and 24430 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively. The magnetic moment of the Co^{II} complex has been found to be 5.2 B.M. which indicates the octahedral structure of the complex⁴. The absorption spectrum of Ni^{II} complex shows two bands at 18610 and 27320 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ (ν_3) transitions respectively. The diamagnetic nature of

Note

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the complexes

Compd.	Colour	μ_{eff} (B.M)	Conductivity $\eta^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Metal (%) : Found (Calcd)
1	C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂ (FO)	Colourless	-	-
1a	[Cu(C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂)Cl ₂]	Dark brown	Paramagnetic	28.2 21.60 (20.82)
1b	[Ni(C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂)Cl ₂]	Pale orange	Diamagnetic	38.4 20.06 (20.24)
1c	[Co(C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	Brown	Paramagnetic	45.6 17.91 (18.24)
2	C ₅ H ₅ NOS (TO)	Colourless	-	-
2a	[Cu(C ₅ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	Brown	Paramagnetic	24.6 19.55 (20.06)
2b	[Ni(C ₅ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	Dark bluish green	Diamagnetic	47.2 18.06 (18.54)
2c	[Co(C ₅ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	Brown	Paramagnetic	27.4 18.13 (18.26)

Table 2. IR spectral data of the ligands and their complexes

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ (cm ⁻¹)
1	C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂ (FO)	1645	2920
1a	[Cu(C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂)Cl ₂]	1625	2920
1b	[Ni(C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂)Cl ₂]	1625	2920
1c	[Co(C ₅ H ₅ NO ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	1625	2920
2	C ₅ H ₅ NOS (TO)	1632	2361
2a	[Cu(C ₅ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	1620	2361
2b	[Ni(C ₅ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	1623	2361
2c	[Co(C ₅ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	1620	2361

the complex and electronic transitions suggest the geometry to be square planar. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex gives two bands one at 12480 cm⁻¹ and another at 17500 cm⁻¹ due respectively to the transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ favouring square planar geometry.

Complexes Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with TO :

The analytical data reflect the metal to ligand stoichiometry to be 1 : 1. The conductivity data of the complexes in DMF (10⁻³ M) suggests their non-electrolytic nature. All the complexes did not react with AgNO₃ solution indicating the non availability ionisable chloride ions and this confirms the chloride ion coordination in the complex.

In the IR spectrum, the ligand band at 1632 cm⁻¹ is

shifted to lower side by 10-20 cm⁻¹ in complexes suggesting the participation of oximine nitrogen in coordination.

The C-S-C band at 1125 cm⁻¹ of the ligand is shifted to 1115 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of complexes and this indicates the involvement of ring sulphur in coordination. Similarly, ν_{OH} band appears at 2361 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of both the ligand and its complexes. This shows the non-involvement of OH in coordination. The N-O stretching of the ligand at 1100 cm⁻¹ has shifted to 1070 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes confirming the coordination through oximino nitrogen.

The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex shows two bands at 14040 and 18450 cm⁻¹, assignable to transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, favouring square planar geometry.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity data of ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.		MIC ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1	C ₂ H ₅ NO ₂ (FO)	50.0	25.0	25.0	40.0
1a	[Cu(C ₂ H ₅ NO ₂)Cl ₂]	10.0	12.5	12.5	6.5
1b	[Ni(C ₂ H ₅ NO ₂)Cl ₂]	25.0	20.0	15.0	13.5
1c	[Co(C ₂ H ₅ NO ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]	40.0	40.0	30.0	40.0
2	C ₃ H ₅ NOS (TO)	50.0	25.0	40.5	40.0
2a	[Cu(C ₃ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	6.0	15.0	15.5	20.5
2b	[Ni(C ₃ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	14.5	15.5	12.5	12.5
2c	[Co(C ₃ H ₅ NOS)Cl ₂]	25.0	25.0	40.0	35.0
	Standard	6.0	12.5	12.5	12.5

In Ni^{II} complex the three bands observed at 15240, 18210 and 21120 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ²A_{1g} → ¹E_g, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B₂ and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}, transitions respectively. This complex is found to be diamagnetic in nature indicating a square planar geometry. The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex shows one band at 16200 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{1g} (P) transition. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 4.54 B.M. Hence tetrahedral geometry is suggested for the Co^{II} complex^{5,6}.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the eight compounds (oximes and complexes) were evaluated for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against *M. tuberculosis*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans* at concentrations of 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ employing the disc method⁷. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values were listed in Table 3. In general the metal complexes are more active than the free oximes. The antimicrobial activity of the metal complexes were found to be in the order : Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II}.

Experimental

Chemicals used were all of AnalaR pure grade. The oximes (ligands FO and TO) were synthesised by refluxing a mixture of aldehyde (0.1 mmol), pyridine (0.1 mmol) and hydroxylammonium chloride (0.1 mmol) in alcoholic medium for an hour. The hot solution was poured into a beaker containing crushed ice with constant stirring until the solid is formed. It was separated by filtration and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous calcium chloride. The resulting product was recrystallised with petroleum ether (60–80 °C).

The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of methanolic solutions of metal salt MCl₂.nH₂O and ligand on a water bath for 1–2 h. The coloured precipitate that appeared on cooling was filtered and washed with alcohol and ether. The resulting solid was dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in vacuum dessiccator. The purity of the compound was checked by TLC using silica gel.

Melting point was determined on a Toshniwal (L-030) apparatus. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambdas 2B spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded at IIT, Chennai. Magnetic moment was measured using Gouy balance.

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